

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring
data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D3.1 DTO-BioFlow data flow blueprint

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D3.1 – DTO-BioFlow data flow Blueprint

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
ARMS	Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures
BGC-Argo	Biogeochemical Argo: the Argo program dedicated to biogeochemical variables including Oxygen, chlorophyll, nutrients etc.
BODC NVS2	British Oceanographic Data Centre NERC (Natural Environment Research Centre) Vocabulary Server 2
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Service / Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
DwC	Darwin Core
DwC-A	Darwin Core Archive
EDITO-infra	EU Public Infrastructure for the European Digital Twin Ocean
EMODnet	European Marine Observation & Data Network
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ETL	Extraction, Transformation and Load
EU DTO	European Union Digital Twin of the Ocean
EurOBIS	European node of Ocean Biodiversity Information System
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GSC	Genomics Standard Consortium
IMIS	Integrated Marine Information System
IPT	Integrated Publishing Toolkit
MlxS	Minimum Information about any (X) Sequence
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OGC EDR	Open Geospatial Consortium Environmental Data Retrieval
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards
WEKEO	WEKEO is one of the 5 Copernicus DIAS (Data and Information Access Services)

Keywords

Genomics, Plankton Imaging, Biologging, Passive acoustics, FAIR, networks, EMODnet, EU DTO, species, products. data

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To understand the current state of marine systems and their pressures, as well as to advance knowledge, it is essential to have comprehensive and accessible marine biodiversity data. Protecting and restoring biodiversity is one of three objectives of the Horizon Europe Mission to restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030, enabling the EU to reach its Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 targets. Within this context, the EU aims to build a digital environment, the EU Digital Twin Ocean (DTO), that allows to create a digital replica of ocean processes to improve their understanding, their response to changes in the system, and to simulate alternative scenarios, which will ultimately allow to make better informed decisions.

Despite previous efforts from the EU, large amounts of biodiversity data still do not find their way into repositories due to several reasons, including cultural, legal, governance issues, lack of resources, or technical barriers. In the case of technical barriers, one of the problems may arise from systems not being able to accommodate for the type of biodiversity data being produced. Various instruments and new techniques can produce vast amounts of data and help to optimise the resources to collect and analyse biodiversity time series data. Nonetheless, the flow of these data into data repositories or integrators is still at distinct stages of development.

The DTO-BioFlow project aims to increase the flow of relevant biodiversity data into the EU DTO. To reach this goal, the project will work on distinct aspects on each work package, each complementing each other. WP2 will target the identification and creation of an inventory of "sleeping" biodiversity data; WP3 will develop sustained flows of new biodiversity data types into the DTO; WP4 will use relevant data from the other WPs to demonstrate with policy relevant use cases the benefits of including new and "sleeping" biodiversity data in an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring; and WP5 will bring the data products developed in all the other WPs into the DTO infrastructure, ensuring that the data and tools produced are interoperable and scalable, and that the architecture is aligned with other Digital Twin Initiatives.

This deliverable presents the DTO-BioFlow data flow Blueprint, a document describing the envisioned data flows for each of the new biodiversity data types produced using different techniques and instruments and that still do not have established dataflows to make them available in data repositories in the long term (i.e. genomics observation networks; plankton imaging observation networks; fish, mammal and bird biologging networks; cetacean passive acoustic observation networks; and other relevant biodiversity data sources). This document will set up the general framework for data flow towards the DTO for each of these biodiversity data types, although the approaches may change as the project evolves if better solutions are needed.

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1. Introduction

To understand the current state of marine systems and their pressures, as well as to advance knowledge, it is essential to have comprehensive and accessible marine biodiversity data. Protecting and restoring biodiversity is one of three objectives of the [Horizon Europe Mission to Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030](#), enabling the EU to reach its [Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 targets](#). Within this context, the EU aims to build a digital environment, the EU Digital Twin Ocean (EU DTO), that allows to create a digital replica of ocean processes to improve our understanding, predict their response to changes in the system, and to simulate alternative scenarios, which will ultimately lead to making better informed decisions.

Despite previous efforts from the EU, large amounts of biodiversity data do not find their way into repositories due to a variety of reasons, for example of a technical nature, when systems are not able to accommodate for the biodiversity data being produced, due to the way they were originally designed. Various instruments and new techniques such as DNA-based observations, plankton imaging observations, passive acoustics, or biologging data, can produce vast amounts of data and help to optimise the resources to collect and analyse biodiversity time series data. Nonetheless, the flow of these data into data repositories or integrators is at distinct stages of development and for some, the guidance is still a work in progress, subject to frequent changes as more information becomes available.

The project DTO-BioFlow aims to increase the flow of relevant biodiversity data into the EU DTO. Work Package (WP) 3 'Enabling sustained flows of biodiversity monitoring data into the DTO', aims to set up the general data flow towards the EU DTO, establishing the connection towards this EU infrastructure and ensuring that sustainable data flows are in place beyond the lifetime of the project. This WP will focus on new biodiversity data types from: (1) genomics observation networks, (2) plankton imaging observation networks, (3) fish, mammal and bird biologging networks, (4) cetacean passive acoustic observation networks, and (5) other relevant biodiversity data sources. These biodiversity data types, some of them quite new to the scientific community, and other relevant biodiversity data sources will contribute data for the demonstration of an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring with policy relevant use cases in WP4 'Demonstrate with policy-relevant use cases'. Ultimately, these data will flow towards the DTO infrastructure developed under other Digital Twin initiatives such as the EDITO-Infra project, with WP5 'Integration in DTO infrastructure' supporting this integration of marine biodiversity data into the EU DTO infrastructure. This interconnection among WPs is planned to build a coherent structure of data sources and use case applications.

The current Blueprint document aims to describe the envisioned data flows for each of the biodiversity data types listed above as discussed during the 'Workshop for drafting DTO-BioFlow data Blueprint' (milestone 5), which took place in December 2023. Nevertheless, to cope with the linkage among WPs and to be able to produce the most sensible products, the data flows described will remain open to improvements throughout the lifetime of the project to ensure that changes can be accommodated, as the tasks in the other WPs evolve.

The following sections of this Blueprint document aim to describe how we envision to set up the general framework for data flows towards the EU DTO for each of the data types in WP3, considering that modifications and updates will be needed as the project progresses. The document is divided in two main chapters:

- **Chapter 2** lists the available integrators and repositories that currently hold any of these biodiversity data types and other data sources, and it describes the general connection of these data to EMODnet Biology as a way to make them available to the EDITO-Infra Data Lake;
- **Chapter 3** is divided into five sections, one for each data type described in the Grant Agreement and above (i.e. genomics, plankton imaging, biologging, passive acoustics, and other relevant biodiversity types and data sources). Each of the data type sections follow the same structure to describe:
 1. Existing data flows for the data type (if any);
 2. Data that is not yet in EMODnet Biology;
 3. Sustainable ingestion procedures into the EU DTO;

4. Envisioned harmonised and fit-for-purpose science-based data products;
5. Test cases and cost-effective biomonitoring;
6. Gaps, unknowns, and developments beyond the DTO-BioFlow project.

2. Integrators and repositories

Chapter 2 focuses on listing the various data integrators and repositories that are available for different data types and how EMODnet Biology fits within the scope of making these new data types available to the EU DTO infrastructure. A brief description of the EU DTO architecture being developed under other EU project initiatives (such as EDITO-Infra), and how DTO-BioFlow data (generated or unlocked) will become available in the DTO Data Lake is also presented.

2.1 Integrator/repository inventory

For the purposes of this document, in this chapter, a distinction is made between data “integrators” and data “repositories”. A data integrator refers to a facility that allows the storage of data and that provides tools that allow for the data to be analysed. The terms integrator and aggregator are used interchangeably throughout the document. In contrast, a data repository is a facility that allows for data storage but does not provide functionalities for data analysis within their platform.

A list of integrators and repositories is provided in Table 1, they are varied in nature: they can be data type specific or manage various types of data; they can be hosted within the organisation of a data originator or externally; and some of them will focus on national scale data, while others have a wider coverage and host/manage data at an international scale. Table 1 does not include data systems created for project purposes and that have no continuous development beyond the scope and lifetime of said project.

Each table section focuses on the known integrators for each data type, organized according to the project tasks (i.e. *Task 3.1: Genomics, Task 3.2: Plankton Imaging, Task 3.3: Biologging, Task 3.4: Passive Acoustics, Task 3.5: Other types of data*). The position of the integrator/repository in the table is not ranked by relevance or importance. At the end of the table there is also a section including known repositories and integrators that publish types of data not included in Tasks 3.1 to 3.4. It is also important to note that the list is not exhaustive and relies on the co-authors' knowledge and community expertise at the time of writing this Blueprint. All links were active at the time this document was published.

Table 1: List of integrators and repositories for the various data types covered by the DTO-BioFlow workplan.

Acronym	Full name	URL	Based in	Geographic scope
Genomics				
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home	United Kingdom	International
MGnify		https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics	United Kingdom	International
IMG/M	Integrated Microbial Genomes & Microbes	https://img.jgi.doe.gov/	United States	International
NMDC	National Microbiome Data Collaborative	https://microbiomedata.org/	United States	International
BOLD	Barcode Of Life Data Systems	https://boldsystems.org/index.php/databases	Canada	International
Qiita		qiita.ucsd.edu	United States	International
MicroEXPERT		https://microexpert.aimicrobiome.cn/	China	International
iMicrobe		https://www.imicrobe.us/	United States	International
metaMicrobesOnline		http://meta.microbesonline.org/	United States	International
MetagenomesOnline		http://metagenomesonline.org/	United States	International
MyGOD		https://mygod.sb-roscoff.fr/public/	France	International
GAPeDNA		https://shiny.cefe.cnrs.fr/GAPeDNA/	France	International
METAREP		https://www.jcvi.org/research/metarep	United States	International
SBDI	Swedish Biodiversity Data Infrastructure	https://asv-portal.biodiversitydata.se/?lang=en-US	Sweden	National
BCO-DMO	Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office	https://www.bco-dmo.org/	United States	International
GEOME	Genomic Observatories Metadatabase	https://geome-ui.org/	United States	International
MicrobiomeDB		https://microbiomedb.org/mbio/app	United States	International
NBDL	National Biodiversity DNA Library	https://research.csiro.au/dnlibrary/	Australia	National
Plankton imaging				
EcoTaxa		https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/	France	International
EcoPart		https://ecopart.obs-vlfr.fr	France	International

SUBSIM		http://subsim.se	Sweden	National
BCO-DMO	Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office	https://www.bco-dmo.org	United States	International
SeaBASS	SeaWiFS Bio-optical and Storage System	https://seabass.gsfc.nasa.gov/	United States	International
BioImage archive		https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/	United Kingdom	International
IDR	Image Data Resource	https://idr.openmicroscopy.org/	United Kingdom	International
Biologging				
Movebank		https://www.movebank.org/cms/movebank-main	Germany	International
ETN	European Tracking Network	https://www.europeantrackingnetwork.org/	Belgium	International
Passive Acoustics				
	ICES Continuous Noise Database	https://underwaternoise.ices.dk/continuous	Denmark	International
	DFO Whale detections	https://www.dfo-mpo.gc.ca/species-especies/mammals-mammiferes/narightwhale-baleinenoirean/alert-alerte/index-eng.html	Canada	National
OPUS	AWI Open Portal to Underwater Soundscapes	https://opus.aq/content.html	Germany	International
NCEI	National Centers for Environmental Information: Passive Acoustic Database	https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/passive-acoustic-data	United States	International
AODN	Australian Ocean Data Network	https://portal.aodn.org.au	Australia	National
MEDIN	Marine Environmental Data and Information Network	https://medin.org.uk/	UK	National
Other data types				
WISE-Marine	Marine information System for Europe	https://water.europa.eu/marine	Denmark	International
iNaturalist		https://www.inaturalist.org/	United States	International
Observation		https://observation.org/	The Netherlands	International

eBird		https://ebird.org/home	United States	International
Plazi		https://plazi.org/	Switzerland	International
OpenBioDiv		https://openbiodiv.net/		International
SIBiLS	Swiss BioInformatics Institute Literature Service	https://www.expasy.org/resources/sibils	Switzerland	International
JCDP	ICES Joint Cetacean Data Programme	https://cetaceans.ices.dk/	Denmark	International
ESAS	European Seabirds At Sea	https://esas.ices.dk/	Denmark	European
AquaMaps		https://www.aquamaps.org/	Canada	International
	German Oceanographic Museum Foundation	https://www.deutsches-meeresmuseum.de/wissenschaft/infothek/datenbanken	German	International
HELCOM	HELCOM Biodiversity database	https://maps.helcom.fi/website/biodiversity/	Finland	International
Ocean Data Platform	Ocean Data Platform	https://www.hubocan.earth/platform	Norway	International
PREGO	Process, environment, organism	https://prego.hcmr.gr/	Greece	International
Repositories that manage and publish other types of data (not included above)				
Acronym	Full Name	URL	Type of data	Scope
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information System	https://www.gbif.org	Various, including those covered by the project	International
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System	https://obis.org	Various, including those covered by the project	International
ArcGIS	ArcGIS Living Atlas of the World	https://livingatlas.arcgis.com/en/home/	Various, including those covered by the project	International
ALA	Atlas of Living Australia	https://www.ala.org.au/	Various, including those covered by the project	Australia
	LifeWatch ERIC	https://www.lifewatch.eu/	Various, including those covered by the project (except genomics)	International
Birds and Habitats directive		https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/datahub	Species occurrences	International
BCG-Argo	BioGeoChemical Argo	https://biogeochemical-argo.org/	Various	International

PANGAEA		https://www.pangaea.de	Various	International
SeaDataNet		https://www.seadatanet.org	Species occurrences	International
Dryad		https://datadryad.org/stash	Various, including those covered by the project	International
GigaDB		http://gigadb.org/	Various, including those covered by the project	International
EMSO ERIC		https://data.emso.eu/	Various, including those covered by the project	International
FinBIF	Finnish Biodiversity Information Facility	https://laji.fi/en	Various, including those covered by the project	National
DASSH	Archive for marine species and habitats data	http://marinebiodiversity.org/	Various, including those covered by the project	National
VertNet		https://vertnet.org/index.html	Various, including those covered by the project	National
biodiversity.aq	SCAR Antarctic Biodiversity Portal	https://www.biodiversity.aq/	Various, including those covered by the project	International
BBDP	Belgian Biodiversity Platform	https://www.biodiversity.be/	Various, including those covered by the project	National
PNDB Data Repository		https://search.dataone.org/portals/PNDB	Various, including those covered by the project	National
NBN Atlas	National Biodiversity Network Atlas	https://nbnatlas.org/	Various, including those covered by the project	National
Dandjoo	Dandjoo biodiversity data platform	https://bio.wa.gov.au/dandjoo	Various, including those covered by the project	National
NGDC	National Genomics Data Center	https://ngdc.cncb.ac.cn/	Various, including those covered by the project	National

BIOTIC	Biological Traits Information Catalogue	https://www.marlin.ac.uk/biotic/	Various	International
Polytraits		http://polytraits.lifewatchgreece.eu	Various	International
Fishbase		https://www.fishbase.se/	Various	International
SeaLifeBase		https://www.sealifebase.ca	Various	International
PLET	Plankton Lifeform Extraction Tool	https://www.dassh.ac.uk/lifeforms/	Various	International
TraitBank		https://traitbank-reconnect.hcmr.gr	Various	International
	Arctic Traits Database	https://arctictraits.univie.ac.at	Various	International
	Marine Species Traits	https://www.marinespecies.org/traits/	Various	International
EOL	Encyclopedia of Life	https://eol.org	Various	International

Aside from the integrators and repositories listed above, there are other platforms that are used as data depositories that can become alternative sources of data, like Zenodo, GitHub, Figshare, DataONE and osf.io. These are not considered integrators or repositories as the search functionalities is not done via the data themselves but through papers or other literature that describes or provides an analysis of the data.

2.2 Inventory of EU projects that will contribute data to EMODnet Biology

In the framework of DTO-BioFlow, this document also identifies several other possible biodiversity data sources stemming from EU funded projects that can contribute to the DTO data lake. Table 2 is an inventory of known ongoing projects (at the time of drafting this Blueprint) that need to ensure that the data they generate becomes available to EMODnet Biology as it is detailed in their Data Management Plans. The list is not exhaustive and relies on the co-authors' knowledge and community expertise at the time of writing.

Table 2: List of ongoing EU funded projects expected to make their data available in EMODnet Biology.

Project name	Website	Lead organisation	Project lifetime	Data type(s)	(Primary) Repository
MARCO-BOLO	https://marcobolo-project.eu/	European Marine Biological Resource Centre (EMBRC)	2022-12-01 to 2026-11-30	Genomics, other (observations, citizen science)	ODIS
EMO BON	https://www.embrc.eu/services/emo-bon/	European Marine Biological Resource Centre (EMBRC)	2021-06 (ongoing)	Genomics, other (observations)	ENA
MARBEFES	https://marbefes.eu/	Institute of Oceanology of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IOPAN)	2022-01-09 to 2023-09-31	Genomics, imaging, acoustics, other (observations, citizen science)	VLIZ
BiOcean5D	https://www.biocean5d.org/	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL)	2022-12-01 to 2026-11-30	Genomics, imaging, acoustics	BiOcean5D data hub (private) and data portal (public), ENA
SUMMER	https://summerh2020.eu/	Centro Tecnológico del Mar y los Alimentos Instituto Tecnológico Pesquero y Alimentario (AZTI)	2019-05-03 to 2024-08-31	Genomics, other (observations)	PANGAEA
iAtlantic	https://www.iatlantic.eu/	The University of Edinburgh	2019-06-01 to 2024-03-31	Genomics, other (observations)	PANGAEA
BRIDGE-BS	https://bridgeblacksea.org/	Middle East Technical University (METU-IMS)	2021-06 to 2025-11	Genomics, other (observations)	ENA, SeaDataNet
OBAMA-NEXT	https://obama-next.eu/	Aarhus University	2022-12-01 to 2026-11-30	Genomics, other (observations)	

MPA Europe	https://mpa-europe.eu/	Nord University	2023-03-01 to 2026-02-28	Blue carbon, species and habitat distributions	OBIS
BiCIKL	https://bicikl-project.eu/	Pensoft Publishers	2021-05-01 to 2024-04-30	Other (literature)	BioDiversity Knowledge Hub

2.3 DTO-BioFlow connection to EMODnet Biology

The European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) Biology is the European Union's service providing free and open access to in situ marine biodiversity data and data products. It is a data integrator that adheres to INSPIRE, Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards for metadata and data and complies with the FAIR principles. EMODnet Biology uses the EurOBIS (European Ocean Biodiversity Information System) data infrastructure to provide for data management. The two initiatives are therefore intrinsically connected and allow for data to reach a wider network of stakeholders through the use of a common data sharing infrastructure with OBIS and GBIF.

Within DTO-BioFlow, the work was planned to ensure that data pipelines are in place for each of the data types addressed in the project, with the aim to maintain a sustained flow of biodiversity data towards EMODnet Biology, and ultimately into the EU DTO infrastructure. Nonetheless, establishing flows to EMODnet Biology and the EU DTO from all the repositories and integrators mentioned in Table 1 is an extremely ambitious task and is beyond the scope and resources of the project.

Data in EMODnet Biology are made interoperable with OBIS and GBIF systems by using the Darwin Core Archive (DwC-A) data standard and the Integrated Publishing Toolkit (IPT) developed by GBIF. This means that all data made available in EMODnet Biology can be harvested by those two integrators via the EurOBIS IPT instance, therefore expanding its visibility and reach. For the purposes of this document, we refer to data flows established to or from EMODnet Biology alone, but with the understanding that these data will also be made available to the two integrators mentioned above. At the time of writing of this document, the main submission pathways to EMODnet Biology are via the IPT, with only a couple of organisations making their data available to EMODnet Biology via direct connection to their in-house systems. In DTO-BioFlow we will explore the implementation of data sharing through web services, automating systems to reduce time consuming procedures and to decrease the introduction of human errors, decrease dependencies and bottlenecks.

The status of the data flows towards EMODnet Biology varies according to the diverse types of data addressed by DTO-BioFlow. In some cases, there is no data flow implemented, in other cases a data flow is already in place and will be subject to improvements during the project's lifetime.

Data flows towards EMODnet Biology for plankton imaging, passive acoustics and other types of data are established for specific integrators/repositories. A comprehensive list of data repositories/integrators which already provide data to EMODnet Biology, as well as additional comments and information is included in Table 3.

Table 3: List of data repositories/integrators which already provide data to EMODnet Biology and improvements to take place within the scope of DTO-BioFlow. (N/A: Not Applicable).

Integrator/Repository	Comments	Work developed under DTO-BioFlow
Plankton imaging		
EcoTaxa	Implemented in EMODnet Biology's Phase III (2019-2021)	Expand data flow for images obtained through various instruments and improve quality control (UVP, ISIS, IFCB, ZooCam, CPICS and CytoSense)
VLIZ ZooScan		Expand to add information on associated particles

VLIZ FlowCam		Expand to add most recent taxonomic revision of dataset and most recent data releases
Passive acoustics		
LifeWatch Belgium	Implemented in EMODnet Biology's Phase III (2019-2021)	Expand data flow for biologging data (especially for ETN)
Other types of data		
ESAS	Implemented in EMODnet Biology's Phase III (2019-2021)	Expand data flow to derived products (density maps)
OBIS		Expand data flow for DNA derived occurrences
GBIF		Expand data flow for DNA derived occurrences
SeaDataNet		N/A

2.3.1 EMODnet Data and Data Product Processing Levels

In order to harmonise the DTO-BioFlow outputs, in terms of data and data products, it was decided to adhere to the Processing Levels established by EMODnet that can be found in the Data and Data Product Portfolio available through the EMODnet website via the following [link](#). These levels are in place for EMODnet and work is ongoing to include these levels in the BODC NVS2, which will allow for an adequate governance structure to the definitions presented in Table 4.

For the purposes of this Blueprint document and to achieve a better harmonisation with EMODnet practices, the anticipated DTO-BioFlow data and data product outputs will be mapped against the levels described in Table 4. A data product is defined as an output resulting from the analysis or modelling of the *in-situ* data and that can include various interpolation techniques and parameters derived from the original data.

Table 4: EMODnet Data and Data Products Processing Level. Information included in the EMODnet Data and Data Product Portfolio document available at <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/communication>.

Level	Description	Applies to
L0	Raw data. Unprocessed instrument data at full resolution, including synchronisation methods (e.g. elimination of CTD up-down duplicates) and excluding communication artifacts.	Data
L1	Full resolution data reconstructed with calibration coefficients, geo-and time-referenced.	
L2	Geo- and time-referenced processed (derived) data with a minimum QC. Near-real time (NRT) with full spatial and/or temporal resolution.	
L3	Delayed mode data with further QC, usually with some completeness, consistency and space/time uniformity. Data QC checks may include comparison with historical data and/or Level 5 products such as climatologies or gridded data.	
L4	Collated data from different measurements, samples and/or sources that have been integrated in a data system by means of standardisation and/or categorisation, and subset or otherwise selected or derived to fulfil a specific requirement. Data can represent numerical values and presence/absence of a category or entity. Integration of datasets at this level enables further QC based on parameter to parameter relationships (e.g. TS diagrams).	
L5	Model or analysis output that uses data of Level 2 and/or 3 as input. Data products of this level represent the spatial distribution of a single parameter derived from multiple measurements. Data are aggregated and undergo some level of geo-processing and spatial or temporal interpolation to cover data gaps and/or solve data discrepancies. L5A. One-dimensional distribution of a specific parameter, without variations on the temporal or depth dimensions.	Data Products

	L5B. Two-dimensional distribution of a specific parameter, with variations on the temporal and/or depth dimensions. L5C. Three-dimensional distribution of a specific parameter.	
L6	Derived information from multi-variable model or analysis that has Level 5 data products and/or Level 2-3 data as input. These input data and data products might have been gathered or developed by the thematic lot itself, by other thematic lots or third parties.	

2.3.2 General Data Flow approach

Within the DTO-BioFlow project, additional data flows towards EMODnet Biology are expected to be implemented although they will always be constrained by the fact that EMODnet Biology can only accept taxonomically annotated data. Because of this, some biological data types are not adequate to become available via EMODnet Biology, e.g. biogenic material that cannot be matched to specific taxa. In the cases of data that cannot go to EMODnet Biology, a direct connection to the EU DTO service will be explored and, where feasible, implemented.

The diagram shown in Figure 1 is a simplified version of the data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow. All activities start with the data collection, which can be done via in situ or remote sensors and/or human observation. Data collected by DTO-BioFlow partners will be subjected to several processing steps (not covered in this diagram). Depending on the type of data, data may be first submitted to an integrator or repository, or directly go into EMODnet Biology. Data in repositories might also be shared with integrators before being made available in EMODnet Biology. In EMODnet Biology, various procedures are implemented to ensure the data are quality checked to avoid publishing data with issues. If issues are encountered, the originators are informed so these can be addressed ahead of publication, thus ensuring that all data are of high quality. All data available via EMODnet Biology will be harvested by the EU DTO and will be findable in the EU DTO Data Lake. This will require a few processing steps, more specifically a reformatting to cloud optimised formats which will allow for faster and more efficient queries.

A second data flow to be considered is the one originating from other EU funded projects (list available in Table 2). Most of the European projects listed in Table 2 will make their data available via data repositories or integrators. From these data repositories or integrators, a data flow to EMODnet Biology should be implemented if non-existing, or improved if already in place. This work can be done with the support of the EMODnet Biology team, but is the responsibility of the projects themselves and will not be addressed in this Blueprint. The final aim is that the data will become available via EMODnet Biology, as well as the EU DTO infrastructure.

Figure 1: Envisaged general data flow diagram towards EMODnet Biology and the EU DTO.

Within EMODnet Biology data will need to pass several quality criteria to be published. This approach is used for data that have not been published before, as well as for data already published in other integrators and or repositories. The

quality criteria followed in EMODnet Biology are described in the [EMODnet GitHub](#) and include integrity, format, visual checks on the data and metadata. As an example, a non-exhaustive list of checks is included below:

- Taxa are matched with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) at genus or (sub)species level. Higher taxonomic levels are also supported, if they can be mapped with an AphiaID or an NCBI Taxonomy ID. The absence of mapping does not constitute a restriction to data publication as these vocabularies are in continuous development and it is common for specimens to not yet have a record when data are ready to be published;
- Latitude and longitude are different from zero and within valid boundaries (i.e. $-90 < \text{latitude} < +90$ and $-180 < \text{longitude} < +180$);
- A valid timestamp is present;
- Biotic and abiotic data are correctly mapped to controlled vocabularies (when those are available).

When data are found to not comply with the above criteria, the data originators/providers are requested to make updates and correct any issues found, thus ensuring that the data are of high quality. If issues are found in the data, and the contact details of data originators/providers are not provided, the severity of the issues is assessed. If the issues do not allow to ensure the quality of the data published, the data will not be included in EMODnet Biology.

2.4 EU DTO Data Lake

The main objective of the project EDITO-Infra –EU Public Infrastructure for the European Digital Twin Ocean, is to build the EU public infrastructure backbone for the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO). This will be done by upgrading, combining, and integrating key service components of the existing EU ocean observing, monitoring and data programmes, namely Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) and EMODnet into a single digital framework. In this context, EDITO-Infra is both the name of the project and the name of the platform that is being developed. As such, EDITO-Infra will provide the foundation for further developments of the EU DTO, hosting the deployment of multiple DTO applications from ongoing and future digital twin projects.

Chapter 3 of the present document provides an overview of the biodiversity data sources for each of the data types in DTO-BioFlow that the project aims to implement a sustainable flow to the EU DTO. The primary strategy is to make those data available via EMODnet Biology, from which a pipeline to EDITO-Infra will be developed. For the data that does not fit the EMODnet data model, the storage component of the EDITO-Infra Data Lake described in this section will be used, thus creating a direct connection to the EU DTO infrastructure.

In EDITO-Infra, a Data Lake is being designed to fulfil two main requirements:

- To allow end-users to easily search, retrieve and add data, by enforcing a metadata framework that ensures standardised and meaningful categorisation of information;
- To provide an efficient retrieval of the data, optimised for both cloud and edge computing.

Essentially, the Data Lake comprises both a catalogue and a storage component. A pivotal aspect of the Data Lake design is the creation of a unified catalogue amalgamating diverse datasets from various integrators and repositories. To propose a comprehensive catalogue to users, a STAC (SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogue) implementation will be used as a technological means to find and easily retrieve assets, i.e the datasets. Data storage within the comprehensive system of EDITO-Infra will provide users with the flexibility to store their scientific data, offering a customisable approach based on individual needs. Users can also choose to integrate their data into organised catalogues for broader accessibility and reuse or can opt to make it private, with access provided only to private catalogues or shared in the public storage that will be available to all users. The Amazon S3 (Simple Storage Service) technology offers a scalable and highly available cloud storage solution well suited for geospatial data. S3's architecture allows for optimised storage and retrieval of Analysis-Ready Cloud-Optimized (ARCO) data and metadata, enabling seamless analysis and processing of

geospatial information in the cloud environment, enhancing accessibility, performance, and cost-effectiveness for data-intensive tasks.

EDITO-Infra will support both in situ data from EMODnet and ERICs, as well as remote sensing data from CMEMS and WEkEO (Figure 2).

A **centralized catalog** provides an **exhaustive list** of all **resources** provided by the *EDITO-Infra* Data Lake.

Figure 2: The EDITO-Infra Data Lake architecture (Source: EDITO-Infra Grant Agreement Figure 2).

3. Data not in EMODnet Biology, sustainable data flows, and anticipated data products

The following chapter focuses on the different data types addressed in DTO-BioFlow. The chapter is split into sub-sections according to the data types as defined in the WP3 tasks, and for consistency, the same topics will be described in each of the sub-sections following the structure below:

1. Existing data flows: details any previously existing data flows towards EMODnet Biology or any other data inventories or repositories;
2. Data not in EMODnet Biology: provides an overview of the data that are currently not available through EMODnet Biology and that the DTO-BioFlow project intends to make accessible via EMODnet Biology;
3. Sustainable ingestion procedures into EMODnet Biology and the EU DTO: details the ingestion of data in EMODnet Biology or directly in the EU DTO if the data cannot be ingested by EMODnet;
4. Extraction and processing into harmonised and fit-for-purpose science-based data products: lists the data products that will be created, some of which will be used in the Demonstrator Use Cases (DUCs) developed within WP4. In addition, details are provided about required data standards, quality assurance, data models, and communication protocols;
5. Test casing and cost-effective biomonitoring: provides information about any testing or development of techniques or instruments that will take place during the project's lifetime;
6. Gaps, unknowns and developments beyond DTO-BioFlow: covers known gaps for the data type as well as data products and developments that would improve the accessibility to data, but which may be beyond the scope, resources and lifetime of the project.

3.1 Genomics

“Genomic data” is an umbrella term used in this document to cover any kind of nucleotide sequence data, irrespective of whether it includes whole genomes, whole transcriptomes, or only specific *loci*. It therefore may refer to the nucleotide sequence information of individual organisms (e.g. for genetic barcoding), as well as of multiple organisms simultaneously by applying the prefix “meta-”. Whole genome sequence data of e.g. microbial community samples will consequently be called “metagenomic” data. In cases where multiple organisms are assessed simultaneously but the focus are individual *loci* (most commonly marker *loci* used for taxonomic identification of species), the term “metabarcoding” is used. Genomic data may include taxonomic and/or functional annotations.

Handling nucleotide sequence data imposes several challenges on data flow management. Firstly, nucleotide sequence data may vary in their storage and computational capacity needs. Secondly, while standards have been developed for the creation of DwC files from such data, those standards can currently incorporate only taxonomic, but not functional annotations (i.e. which taxa are in the sample, but not which genes; see section 3.1.4).

In the scope of this project, we will mainly focus on taxonomically annotated nucleotide sequence data derived from environmental DNA (eDNA) samples subjected to either metabarcoding or metagenomic sequencing or both. Hence, we will be using the term “genomics” hereafter to refer to these types of approaches. Environmental DNA (eDNA) refers to DNA that can be extracted from environmental samples such as soil, water or air (without any taxon targeted isolation first) (Taberlet et al., 2012) and it can derive from a variety of sources, such as shedding from organisms, cell lysis or biologically active propagules (Rodriguez-Ezpeleta et al., 2021). Genomics datasets in DTO-BioFlow will be created from analysis of eDNA derived from water filters (micro- and nanoplankton) and from hard substrate (from Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures, ARMS).

3.1.1 Existing data flows

Currently, there is no established genomics data flow to EMODnet Biology. However, in some cases, there is an existing data flow from the raw sequence data to DwC occurrence files deposited in other data repositories. The flow starts from the submission of the raw sequence files to ENA, a repository run by EMBL-EBI, EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute, or NCBI or DDBJ, which are all INSDC repositories. Upon user request, the MGnify platform of EMBL-EBI analyses nucleotide sequence data (either publicly available on ENA or user's privately ENA stored data) and taxonomically annotates individual sequences using reference databases. MGnify is also periodically analysing publicly available ENA nucleotide sequence data. The taxonomically annotated data is subsequently fetched by GBIF.

While most raw sequence data are deposited into a data repository and/or integrator, the processed data, i.e. the intermediate and/or results of the raw data analysis, are rarely deposited in repositories in a structured manner. They may be included in scientific publications as supplementary material or accessible from general purpose online repositories (e.g. Dryad, Zenodo, GitHub, etc.).

3.1.2 Data not in EMODnet Biology

At the time of drafting this document, genomics data are not available through EMODnet Biology, see section 3.1.3. In DTO-BioFlow, data flow from MGnify will be prioritised, since it is considered one of the most important and valuable integrators and since it is based on ENA, one of the INSDC repositories (see Table 1).

As computational capabilities are not unlimited and because not all ENA data have already been analysed by MGnify, DTO-BioFlow will select specific datasets to be prioritised for analysis by MGnify, focusing on datasets created in the framework of monitoring networks and projects that are collected respecting the Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) principles of the Nagoya Protocol, e.g. EMO BON data. Another priority should be to facilitate ways for researchers to submit their eDNA derived data products directly to EMODnet Biology and consequently the EU DTO. GBIF has recently implemented an eDNA tool to facilitate the submission of user processed genomics data, i.e. analysis outputs of raw sequence data (e.g. taxa per sample tables, processed sequences, etc). Similarly, OBIS has a GitHub repository with code examples on how to convert eDNA metabarcoding data to DwC prior to submission to OBIS. If these developments were merged or if novel tools were developed, it could help mobilise sleeping data from personal computers and institutional High-Performance Computing (HPC) clusters to EMODnet Biology, thus enhancing the flow of genomics data into the EU DTO.

3.1.3 Sustainable ingestion procedures into EMODnet Biology and the EU DTO

As previously mentioned, at the time of writing this document, there is no established data flow of genomics towards EMODnet Biology. The publication of genomics data is being developed under EMODnet Biology and a first implementation will be operational by May 9th, 2025 (end date of the current EMODnet Biology contract). The publication of genomics data is an EU requirement for EMODnet Biology and work is ongoing at technical (changes to the database and associated data publication procedures) and data management level (i.e. through the publication of submission guidelines for data providers) to ensure this objective is met in a timely manner.

A first approach in establishing sustainable data flows towards EMODnet Biology is to reuse existing flows towards GBIF (see 3.1.1), therefore, we will explore the feasibility of setting up a data flow directly from MGnify or other integrators like GBIF to EMODnet Biology, which, because the data are interoperable, should not have unsurmountable constraints for the data that meets EMODnet Biology's quality criteria (see 2.3.2). In addition, if other genomics data already exist in GBIF and/or OBIS, for example data deposited directly by users or projects, they could also be harvested and republished into EMODnet Biology, provided they meet the required quality criteria.

Genomics-dependent criteria that need to be met when such data are ingested into EMODnet Biology concern the taxonomic annotations of the raw nucleotide sequence data. Erroneous taxonomic annotations are a common issue when dealing with genomics data, as well as occurrence of terrestrial or freshwater species in marine datasets, and vice versa. This must be addressed in a dataset specific way, as for some datasets containing samples from habitats and

locations in the land-sea interface, e.g. datasets from estuaries, it is reasonable to expect terrestrial species; however, it is anomalous to find such occurrences in e.g. deep-sea datasets. In addition, sequences annotated as human might potentially occur in genomics data from contamination during the library preparation; such sequences will be removed from the datasets. In general, quality control procedures need to be designed and implemented at this stage to ensure the data are free of any issues like the ones described above. Another important quality (two-fold) issue that will be dealt with, is the accuracy of the taxonomic identifications. Firstly, in case confidence estimates or bootstrap values adjacent to the taxa identifications are provided, they will be used to flag data as erroneous or uncertain if the aforementioned estimates/values fall below certain thresholds. Secondly, the accuracy of taxonomic annotations mainly depends on the taxonomic resolution of the genetic locus (or loci), on the completeness of reference databases and on how easy it is to identify the taxa through the conventional way, i.e. easy to identify taxa will have more accurately identified sequences available in reference databases.

The diagram included in Figure 4 is a schematic depiction of the genomics data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow. All activities will start with the data obtained from material samples which in most cases are collected by humans, although there can be cases where collection can be assisted and/or implemented by automated sampling devices. Automated devices are often also used after sample collection, e.g. for the PCR amplification and library preparation to minimise error rates and the hands-on time for the molecular analyses.

Genomics data created and/or collected by DTO-BioFlow partners and associated projects can be submitted to data repositories or integrators; in the last case, data will undergo quality control steps dependent on the chosen integrator. Data in repositories might also be shared with integrators, after going through quality control steps as mentioned previously, or they can become directly available in EMODnet Biology. Data from integrators can be either harvested from EMODnet Biology, or directly by the EU DTO in case they are data that do not fit EMODnet Biology's data infrastructure. In EMODnet Biology, various procedures are implemented to ensure the data are quality checked to avoid publishing data with issues, in addition, specific procedures for the genomics data will be implemented, as mentioned previously. Specific attention will be given to the Strategy for addressing the Ethics of DTO-BioFlow (not published at the time of writing) according to which all project data should respect the principles of [ABS of the Nagoya Protocol](#). This means that extra quality control steps would need to be taken. Repositories and integrators are not requesting ABS metadata upon sequence submission since they are not obliged to adhere to the Nagoya protocol; therefore, there might be cases where genomics data are not adhering to the Nagoya Protocol. To overcome this issue, the ABS focal points of the countries where the material samples were collected will be contacted to request whether the genomics data are classified as genetic resources in the country of origin, and whether permission/authorisation is necessary for inclusion of the relevant data in EMODnet Biology and the EU DTO.

All data made available via EMODnet Biology will eventually be made available to the EU DTO and will be Findable, Accessible and Reusable in the DTO Data Lake.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram showing the anticipated genomics data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow

3.1.4 Extraction and processing into harmonised and fit for purpose science-based data products

Genomics data products will be EMODnet level 3 products (see Table 4). The main data product types that will be produced will be occurrence data of biological taxa in delimiter-separated tabular format, which will be annotated with literature information for species of interest, and environmental metadata, which can be retrieved from ENA BioSamples or from other repositories (e.g. PANGAEA). The creation of gene occurrence tables will be revisited at a later stage within the DTO-BioFlow project but, this work is not considered a priority at the moment.

In addition, it is envisioned that genomics data will be used in two of the WP4 Demonstrator Use Cases (DUC): DUC-1 on invasive species management and DUC-3 on assessment of plankton diversity in relation to human impact. Existing workflows for metagenomic and metabarcoding analyses will be further developed to create useful data products for downstream analysis.

3.1.4.1 Implementation of standards, quality assurance, data models and communication protocols

Genomics data should be submitted to repositories and/or integrators using the GSC MIxS (Minimum Information about any (X) Sequence) checklists. Taxa occurrence tables should be formatted to DwC files using the Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) DNA derived data extension, which incorporates MIxS terms into the DwC standard. Quality control procedures will be developed to validate raw genomic data and prepare them for downstream analyses. Revision of data models and specifications for data exchange and semantic interoperability will be implemented to improve publication and discovery of genetic data in OBIS.

Lately, efforts have been made to align standards for genomics data and reach a sustainable Darwin Core-MIxS Interoperability (Meyer et al., 2023). In addition, initiatives such as the Minimum Information for an Omic Protocol (MIOP) proposed and developed by the Better Biomolecular Ocean Practices (BeBOP) project are positive steps towards the enhancement of standards' implementation and interoperability.

3.1.5 Test casing and cost-effective biomonitoring

Certain test cases have been identified in the framework of the DTO-BioFlow project regarding adapted cost-effective protocols for EMO BON (genomics) data. More specifically, alternative ARMS sampling protocols will be tested which will entail recoverable moorings for the ARMS units. Furthermore, usage of low-cost consumables and/or lower sample volumes will be also tested and, if successful, they could potentially replace the current ones. Moreover, different genomic techniques will be also tested, examples of which include sequencing of zooplankton and/or metabarcoding sequencing aiming at fish populations, both on samples already collected in the framework of EMO BON. Lastly, the use of citizen scientists for water sample collection can be considered as a low-cost step in DNA based biomonitoring.

3.1.6 Gaps, unknowns, developments beyond DTO-BioFlow

One major issue associated with genomics data is their interlinkage with the high-throughput sequencing developments; new platforms are replacing older ones, while introducing new chemistries and protocols. Inevitably, pipelines and tools built to analyse such data are also becoming obsolete. Thus, it is exceedingly difficult to re-analyse older raw data produced by discontinued platforms to create the desired taxa occurrence tables. However, re-analysis of existing data is critical as more complete reference databases can reveal information that was previously inaccessible.

One of the data products of interest for the genomic data is the creation of gene occurrence tables mentioned in section 3.1.4. The project will evaluate the feasibility of incorporating these data into the project data infrastructure at a later stage, although it may be beyond the resources currently available on the project.

3.2 Plankton Imaging

Plankton imaging data covers all data taken by quantitative imaging instruments, i.e. instruments that take a large quantity of images, in a consistent manner, to reliably extract quantitative information, such as concentrations and/or biovolumes. The instruments deployed *in situ* mainly image marine snow, which constitutes 80% to 90% of the particles in the water. When samples are processed shortly after collection, laboratory instruments can also help quantify the abundance of these particles, which play an essential role in marine systems, as they export carbon to the deep ocean through the biological pump.

There is a wide variety of instruments that can collect imaging data *in situ* or in the laboratory, each one with its own workflow. It is envisioned that imaging data will flow into the EU DTO, mostly via data integrators/repositories, from these instruments, which are deployed across several *in situ* observation networks, notably including those overseen by DTO-BioFlow partners. The improved flows of plankton imaging data expected from this project will enhance biomonitoring efforts and global carbon flux estimations.

3.2.1 Existing data flows

After collection, images are processed, usually to extract Regions Of Interest (ROIs) from full frames and to measure them in numerous ways. This processing is usually performed with software specific to each instrument, although efforts are underway within the project to develop an instrument-agnostic pipeline (PyOPIA) that can be configured to treat images from an array of instruments. For some *in situ* instruments, the processing is two-fold: (1) detecting and sizing all objects, resulting in “particle-level” information (see below), and (2) extracting the ROIs, which follows the usual data flow. Together with data collection and initial pre-processing, a first set of quality controls are usually performed, mostly on the metadata (location, date, etc.).

These ROIs need to be classified taxonomically, which is frequently done with the help of machine learning algorithms within data repositories. The images that undergo an initial machine learning-based classification can later be validated by taxonomic experts before they are submitted to data aggregators, the fact that this validation occurs or not depends on the institute and sensor being used and on the feasibility of locating the adequate human resources to perform it. One popular platform to do so is EcoTaxa (Sorbonne University/CNRS), but the use of other platforms such as Subsim (University of Gothenburg), PLAVA (VLIZ) or PySilcam/PyOPIA (SINTEF) will also be explored in the project. Once the classification is performed, the occurrences (and associated variables, such as concentrations, biovolumes or even individual measurements of size, opacity, etc.) are exported as a DwC-A and uploaded to an IPT instance from where it follows the standard EMODnet Biology procedures that lead to data publication.

This overall data flow is already functional for monitoring time series collected with specific instruments such as the ZooScan, FlowCam, some ROVs (Remotely Operated Vehicles), and camera traps. Nonetheless, improvements can be made, which is the goal of this and other synergistic projects (see below).

Figure 4: Schematic diagram showing the plankton imaging data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow

3.2.2 Data not in EMODnet Biology

Several types of data resulting from plankton imaging are not in EMODnet Biology. In this section we focus on 'particle data' and 'particle and taxonomic data processed on remote vectors'.

Particle data

In addition to images of living organisms, imaging instruments collect many images of particles. This is particularly true for deployments of the Underwater Vision Profiler (UVP) or the Continuous Particle Imaging Classification System (CPICS). These data do not currently flow to EMODnet Biology, since EMODnet Biology can only accept taxonomically annotated data.

The UVP collects *in situ* images, counts and sizes for all particles larger than $\sim 100\mu\text{m}$, and extracts ROIs for large particles ($>1\text{mm}$). The counting, sizing, and image segmentation are done by the instrument itself. For UVP5s and UVP6s installed on ships, gliders, moorings etc., these pre-processed data are stored in the application EcoPart and the ROIs are sent to EcoTaxa for taxonomic identification. EcoPart structures its information by size and exports depth-resolved particle size spectra; it also retrieves the taxonomic identifications from EcoTaxa to export concentrations for the taxonomically identified large particles (including plankton). EcoTaxa currently does not have the adequate metadata to compute these concentrations and is only able to export occurrences (with imprecise depth) as DwC-A.

The CPICS functions in an analogous way but does not have a software suite in EcoPart and EcoTaxa to handle its data. While work is ongoing to include the ROIs from the CPICS in EcoTaxa (organisms, see above), the particle data have not been considered yet. One possibility is to focus on the flow of ROI-derived data only; it would go through EcoTaxa and follow the process outlined in the previous section to the EU DTO. Another possibility is to integrate the CPICS particle data into EcoPart, and subsequently to the EU DTO. Discussions are ongoing as to the feasibility of these two approaches.

Because these particle data lack taxonomic information, they do not fit the EMODnet Biology's data infrastructure, they will either be sent from EcoPart directly to the EDITO-Infra Data Lake for incorporation in the EU DTO, or they will be aggregated in an intermediate EU-level repository/integrator that is able to receive particle data and will subsequently be harvested from this aggregator by the EU DTO. This repository/aggregator is yet to be identified, but possible candidates are other EMODnet thematics, or SeaDataNet.

In order to implement the flow of particle data from EcoPart, the development of an Application Programming Interface (API) is planned for DTO-BioFlow. This will enable the necessary machine-to-machine interactions with the EU DTO or other integrators to produce a fully automatic pipeline. Since EcoPart holds raw particle data, it can be aggregated *ad hoc*, at chosen depth and time resolutions.

Particle and taxonomic data processed on remote vectors

When imaging instruments are deployed on remote vectors (e.g. the UVP6 on Biogeochemical (BGC)-Argo floats, the SilCam on various moorings), classification need to be performed in the instrument itself, to provide real time information or decrease the communication bandwidth usage. In these cases, it may not be possible for a human to check individual classifications as the data may be sent in a pre-aggregated form.

For the UVP deployed on Argo floats, the data are sent back through satellite communication to the Argo data centres. To lower the cost of communication, the data are summarised per bin depth. In addition, the large ROIs need to be classified on the float by an embedded automatic classification model (in ~ 20 categories) instead of being sent back on shore for later classification. This classification is an optional feature that consumes energy and might not always be implemented. The data sent to the Argo centres, which undergo various standard Argo checks, are size spectra (from $100\mu\text{m}$ upwards) per fixed depth bins and, when available, concentrations of plankton in the same bins. Particle and taxonomic data are not yet an official BGC-Argo variable, although efforts are underway to include UVP6 data, so they

are stored as a separate set of binary files, in NetCDF format, in the Argo repositories. BCG-Argo variables currently include Oxygen, Chlorophyll, BBP (particulate optical backscattering), Nitrate, pH and Irradiance.

For particle data collected on Argo floats, two possible workflows to the EU DTO are envisioned. One option is to use EcoPart as the sole UVP data repository, since it is already the distributor of non-Argo UVP data and can fetch data from the Argo repository, host the data, send it to the EU DTO following the EcoPart-EU DTO pipeline and, in return, send relevant statistics to Argo (so that Argo can track data distribution). The second option is to link the NetCDF files stored in the Argo repository directly to the EU DTO, bypassing EcoPart. In both cases, these files will have the same format, which will contribute to a more streamlined automation protocol and data flow. The assessment of these two approaches is ongoing and the most feasible solution will be implemented within the project's lifetime. Regarding the taxonomic identifications carried out on these remote vectors, the error rate, the impossibility to confirm their quality, and the fact that they are pre-aggregated on wide and predefined bins means that we do not plan for these identifications to flow to the EU DTO within this project.

The SilCam (a telecentric system) was initially developed to measure large particulate pollutants in seawater. The system has been used both in large-scale experimental subsea releases of oil and gas, and in the field to quantify the distribution of suspended material such as zooplankton, large phytoplankton, mineral grains and marine snow. It is used to collect data in the ocean observatory in the Trondheim fjord and on research cruises. Images are analysed to provide object size distributions and concentrations, spanning from ~50µm to several cm in length. Deep Convolutional Neural Networks are used to identify the type of particle (e.g. a copepod, diatom chain, marine snow, etc.). True, in-focus particle images are recorded directly in colour, so minimal processing is needed. These images are very similar to microscope images (albeit with a lower magnification). A typical image (of 15MB) is processed in about 0.7s to retrieve particle size distribution, concentration, and classified particle types within the image. Particle images and statistics are obtained from the PySilCam software, which was integrated into PyOPIA as part of the [Iliad project](#) to enable device independent image analysis and particle classification for both the SilCam and other instruments, including the LISST (particle size analyser and counter that can also provide measurements of sediment concentration) and UVP. This fully automated, "on the edge" classification pipeline will be directly connected to the EU DTO as part of Iliad and the actions in DTO-BioFlow will further this integration.

3.2.3 Sustainable ingestion procedures into EMODnet Biology and the EU DTO

While the flow of some plankton imaging data to EMODnet Biology is already functional (described in section 3.2.1), this will be improved for various data integrators/repositories within the scope of the DTO-BioFlow project.

SUBSIM: Is an open-source platform for processing macroscopic image data derived from camera-based sensors (<http://subsim.se>). ROVs and underwater camera trap systems such as e.g., baited remote underwater video (BRUV); are beginning to deliver standardised plankton image data for macro- and megaplankton with size ranges from 2 – 300cm. Datasets are not very consistent but quickly building up in size offering possibilities to create valuable data products from macroscopic species observations. The SUBSIM platform includes essential functions for image/movie data management, digital collaboration, machine learning and high-performance computing. Input data are image and movie files, in various formats, accompanied with essential metadata. Output data from the plankton image analyses include species observations in the water column in form of DwC-A files, object detection models and model test statistics as well as image reference libraries (i.e., training data). Improvements will be made by establishing communication protocols to EMODnet Biology, elaborating and implementing data and metadata standards, as well as Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), for fieldwork and monitoring programs. These planned improvements are further detailed in section 3.2.4.1.

EcoTaxa: As previously described, a functioning pipeline between EcoTaxa and EMODnet Biology already exists for several instruments (notably the ZooScan). In the months following the publication of this document and thanks to work carried out in other projects (notably BlueCloud2026), users will be able to extract occurrence, concentration, and biovolume data for several other standard plankton imaging instruments (FlowCam, UVP, ISIS, IFCB, ZooCam). Through

other projects, like JERICO-S3, input pipelines from the sensor to EcoTaxa will be functional for the CPICS and CytoSense instruments, which will then benefit from the same export capabilities.

All these data flows will increase the ingestion of data from various monitoring programs into the EU DTO and DTO-BioFlow will also provide data quality improvements to these data flows, which are further described below. One important caveat, however, is that not all data from EcoTaxa will be accessible in the EU DTO. EcoTaxa is a tool used by researchers to process their data while retaining full ownership over it; only the data owner can decide to export it as Dwc-A and publish to EMODnet Biology. While the partners involved in this project will ensure that their data are accessible, the project cannot ensure that all data in EcoTaxa will be made available to either EMODnet Biology or the EU DTO.

LifeWatch Observatory: A ZooScan-to-EMODnet Biology pipeline from the LifeWatch Marine Observatory already exists for zooplankton occurrences and concentrations, but information on associated particles needs to be added to the existing data. The LifeWatch FlowCam-to-EMODnet Biology for phytoplankton occurrences and concentrations also needs to reflect the latest taxonomic revision of the dataset and latest data releases. Both pipelines will include environmental data, essentially nutrient, pigment and CTD data (temperature, conductivity, depth among other variables), added to the collected biodiversity data.

3.2.4 Extraction and processing into harmonised and fit for purpose science-based data products

In addition to the provision of point occurrences to the EU DTO (EMODnet level 2 or 3 data), two sets of data products are envisioned as part of WP4 Demonstrator Use Cases (DUCs):

1. DUC 4.3 will work on pelagic habitat indicators under descriptor 1 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). Methods for these indicators have been largely worked out in the OSPAR/HELCOM working groups but have mainly been applied on microscopic count data from traditional monitoring. We will showcase that data from high-throughput imaging (in DUC 4.3) and next generation sequencing (in the project MARCO-BOLO) can also be used in indicator calculations in a Belgian test site case study. In doing so we will upgrade existing analytical tools and integrate them into a stable and open-access environment in collaboration with the authors;
2. In DUC 7, we will create maps of carbon export (EMODnet level 5 product) at global scale with some time resolution (e.g. seasonal). This will involve all the particle data presented above, collated with environmental fields which will be used for extrapolation.

These products will be provided to the EU DTO and possibly distributed through EMODnet Biology.

3.2.4.1 Implementation of standards, quality assurance, data models and communication protocols

For each data integrator/repository, work will be focused on improving data standards and quality.

EcoTaxa: The development will be focused on improving quality control procedures and communication protocols for sensor-to-EcoTaxa and EcoTaxa-to-EMODnet Biology. Most of the effort will be on data from the UVP. As explained above, for this instrument, the appropriate metadata (i.e., depth and volume imaged) is not in EcoTaxa and will need to be synchronised automatically between the source data, in EcoPart, and EcoTaxa. An additional development is to introduce quality control procedures in EcoTaxa that match the ones performed by the BioCheck tool. These checks are currently only applied after the data are extracted from EcoTaxa but including them in EcoTaxa itself will allow data providers to identify any issues earlier in the data chain.

EcoPart: As no standards currently exist for marine particle data, they will need to be defined in a way that is compatible with the BGC-Argo program to ensure homogeneity between products from instruments deployed on ships, gliders and Argo floats. This work is planned in both EcoPart and the Argo data centres. Terms from the BODC NVS2 will be used

wherever relevant, and new terms will be requested and created as needed. In terms of quality control, metadata checks (position, depth, time) will mirror those performed by the BioCheck tool, and basic range checks will be implemented in terms of particle concentrations. The full suite of checks is being defined and will evolve throughout the project to ensure that those implemented are suitable and in place by the end of the project.

PyOPIA: To establish a data flow from PySilCam/PyOPIA to the EU DTO, data currently processed as binary files (e.g. NetCDF) will need to be transformed to a format used in this infrastructure (e.g. zarr/STAC) and served through a defined API (e.g. OGC EDR). Current work developed by Iliad will also establish semantic harmonisation between the data and metadata.

LifeWatch observatory: Currently, biodiversity data and associated environmental data collected in the framework of the LifeWatch Marine Observatory are subject to some quality assurance steps and mapped with vocabularies from the BODC NVS2 to maintain a standardised dataset. Essentially, taxon match with WoRMS is performed, automatic checks of metadata (e.g., position, time) are issued, each ROI is manually validated to maintain a 100% accuracy, SOPs and dataflows are described and published in detailed data papers, and the resulting DwC-A archives are checked against the BioCheck tool and once the data are ready, they published on a yearly basis. Script-based workflows will be upgraded to include the flow of additional relevant metadata to EMODnet Biology and to include additional quality control steps, it is also envisaged that the scripts will become open access.

SUBSIM: The development will focus on elaborating input data and metadata standards according to guidelines and data models developed by GBIF (<https://doi.org/10.35035/doc-0qzp-2x37>) and TDWG (<https://camtrap-dp.tdwg.org>). This work will be accompanied by the development of SOPs for fieldwork and monitoring programs. Another focus will be on improving the existing communication protocols to automate the harvesting of species observation data from SUBSIM into EMODnet Biology, a process which will also include quality control functionalities. Lastly, some of the existing monitoring programs collecting movie/image data (e.g., on invasive fish monitoring) will be used to test the interoperability and data flows between SUBSIM and EMODnet Biology and scrutinise the reproducibility of the data products delivered.

3.2.5 Test casing and cost-effective biomonitoring

The increase of data flows from regular monitoring programs performed through imaging will be an index of the success of this work. Test cases are identified for the ZooScan, FlowCam and CPICS instruments, used by partners of the project in the Mediterranean Sea, as well as the Belgian and German parts of the North Sea. But of course, the developments achieved should be beneficial to other imaging data providers outside of the project.

In addition, there is currently no centrally aggregated data on marine particles. The creation of a functional data flow that will ensure the continuous integration of new data will be useful to the community. It will be coordinated with other international endeavours with similar (but not identical) goals, such as <http://pssdb.net>.

3.2.6 Gaps, unknowns, developments beyond DTO-BioFlow

Cytosense: This instrument is an in-flow device that can provide both cytometric measurements (a “pulse shape”, at various wavelengths, for each cell) and images (but only for a selection of large objects). These, scarce, images can be classified following the data flow in EcoTaxa described above. They can provide information on occurrences and on relative abundance but not concentrations/biovolumes since they constitute only a partial view of the community.

Pulse shapes, however, are more difficult to deal with. First, they represent many more objects and are therefore a challenge to handle. Second, the inter-comparability between instruments is low and makes data integration at a global scale very difficult; for example, a model trained to identify organisms from the pulse shapes on one instrument may not work on another instrument with different settings. Finally, pulse shapes often only allow the discrimination of broad functional groups, with no clear taxonomic designation. These obstacles, however, could be partially overcome by transferring the taxonomic labels applied to images to the corresponding pulse shapes, training an automatic classifier on these labelled pulse-shapes, and applying this classifier to the whole archive of pulse shapes.

Notwithstanding classification errors by the automated classifier, this would result in exhaustive taxonomic labels that could then be used to provide occurrences as well as concentrations. Abundances for characterized species could then be sent to EMODnet Biology. Within DTO-BioFlow (as well as other projects), work is planned to gather images, match pulse-shapes, manually cluster samples, and continue working on an automated classifier. IFCB and FlowCam images will also be sent to EcoTaxa to test classifiers in EcoTaxa. If this work is successful, cytometric data can then be incorporated in the EU DTO via EcoTaxa.

Macroscopic plankton imaging: Imaging methods for organisms >2cm are widespread but there are few standards for methods or data. Given the enormous potential of macroscopic image analysis and the broad application of macroscopic image sensors in e.g., BRUVs, ROVs, and GoPro setups, it is important to develop field protocols, data standards, and interoperability functions for macroscopic images. Ongoing efforts, such as Camtrap DP (<https://camtrap-dp.tdwg.org/>), FathomNet (<https://www.mbari.org/data/fathomnet/>), CoralNet (<https://coralnet.ucsd.edu>) and SUBSIM (<http://subsim.se>) are a starting point to improve data flows of macroscopic images into the EU DTO.

3.3 Biologging

Biologging data are data of animal positions/presences obtained by animal-borne electronic devices. For this project, we consider biologging data from animals tagged in Europe, with mainly marine positions. These data are typically stored in Movebank and ETN, both hosted in Europe and can be divided into three types: GPS tracking, archival tracking, and acoustic telemetry.

GPS tracking: involves electronic devices (such as GPS and SPOT tags) that record GPS positions. It is a technique that can be used for (marine) taxa with a large enough body size to carry a tag, and that live above or near the water surface so that a connection can be established with GPS satellites. Relevant taxa are large birds, marine mammals (cetaceans), fish (i.e. sharks) and marine reptiles (turtles). These type of data are managed in Movebank.

Archival tracking: uses electronic tags which store environmental data like water temperature, pressure (i.e. depth), acceleration, and light. The data are either downloaded from a detached and retrieved device (data storage tags) or directly sent through the ARGOS satellite system (e.g. pop-off satellite archival tags or PSATs). The trajectory of the animal can then be reconstructed through geolocation and hence requires processing of the raw data. These type of data can be managed in ETN.

Acoustic telemetry: uses a network of receivers that detect animal-borne acoustic transmitters when they pass in close vicinity of a receiver, a technique mainly used for fishes and crustaceans. The transmitters emit an acoustic signal (on a fixed frequency) with a unique ID on a predefined time interval and as the tagged animal moves through a network of receivers, it generates a trajectory. Detection range and therefore position resolution is 200m on average, albeit being highly dependent on prevailing environmental conditions. These type of data are managed in ETN.

3.3.1 Existing data flows

Biologging data undergo the following steps from raw to analysis-ready data:

1. Data are collected by the tag (GPS and archival telemetry) or receiver (acoustic telemetry);
2. Data are transmitted to the ARGOS satellite system or downloaded to a personal computer;
3. Data are uploaded to ETN (for acoustic telemetry and archival tracking) or Movebank (for GPS tracking). This step involves transforming the data to the model used by these systems, a process that is aided by a mapping interface for both Movebank and ETN;
4. Data are associated with a project and documented with metadata on the animals, tags, and deployments. Project metadata are maintained and made publicly available in the [Integrated Marine Information System \(IMIS\)](#) for ETN and a [data catalogue](#) for Movebank;
5. Collaborators are granted access to the project to explore or download data. Programmatic access to the data is facilitated by the R packages [etn](#) for ETN and [move2](#) for Movebank.

Data are not operationally shared with EMODnet Biology, however data from biologging projects that are part of LifeWatch Belgium have been published as open data. The data were formatted as a [Data Package](#) and published as a [Marine Data Archive](#) for ETN, and a Zenodo deposit for Movebank. The latter GPS tracking data were also transformed and published as Darwin Core Archive that are available in GBIF and OBIS and harvested from one of these aggregators by EMODnet Biology ([example](#)).

ETN and the Ocean Tracking Network (OTN) perform a direct exchange of higher level ‘discovery’ metadata, as well as locations of receivers. With this exchange it is possible to check if any of the tags from a reported project are found on each other data systems, thus preventing duplication; matching tags directly to detections is not possible yet. Some tracking projects that are performed in Europe have OTN as their primary data repository (linked to loaner programs).

Figure 5: Schematic diagram showing the biologging data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow.

3.3.2 Data not in EMODnet Biology

The following biologging data are not in EMODnet Biology:

1. GPS tracking data in Movebank that is not part of LifeWatch Belgium;
2. Acoustic telemetry data in ETN;
3. Archival data in ETN;
4. All data of the abovementioned technologies on personal computers.

3.3.3 Sustainable ingestion procedures into EMODnet Biology and the EU DTO

The first step towards sustainable ingestion is to make sure biologging data make it to the two main integrators in Europe: ETN and Movebank. This requires outreach, training, and support of researchers owning biologging data. Such services are already provided by the maintainers of those integrators, VLIZ and Max Planck Institute of Animal Behavior, respectively. Developing ingestion procedures from those systems is not only technically more efficient, but it also builds upon their outreach capacity.

Darwin Core is well suited to standardise biologging data, recorded animal positions can be expressed as machine observations grouped into deployments as parent events. The capture, tagging, release, and optional recapture events can be included as human observations. Both types of observations can have associated measurements that can be expressed in the DwC MeasurementOrFact extension, e.g. biometrics taken when the animal was captured, or measurements recorded by the tag. Since biologging data can be recorded at very high frequencies, they should be subsampled before use or ingestion into an aggregator. Subsampling (not averaging) by hour supports most use cases and is the best practice for both acoustic telemetry and GPS tracking. Archival data need additional processing before it can be presented in DwC.

3.3.4 Extraction and processing into harmonised and fit for purpose science-based data products

Within this project, a number of science-based products will be developed based on the raw observation data to enable users' access and overview of the data. Products will focus on, but not limited to, automated report files providing a summary of the tagged animals within a specific time frame or project, animal tracks and device maintenance reports. In addition, dynamic maps will be developed to map the detections or presences of tagged animals. This will be done in relevant software and use, for instance leaflet applications with a 'moving time' function to view the spatio-temporal movement. Finally, we will develop the fundamentals to integrate a geolocation model in the dataflow, which will allow the estimate of daily positions of animals tracked with archival tags.

3.3.4.1 Implementation of standards, quality assurance, data models and communication protocols

We will improve and extend the standards and tools set up for the biologging data flow towards ETN and Movebank and exchange with EMODnet Biology/OBIS/GBIF through Darwin Core. In addition, existing data exchange routines will be extended for archival and satellite tracking data.

Related to the ETN database in particular, standard metadata sheets (.csv files for tags, animals, receivers and deployment information) are already in place for users to import data into ETN. This ensures data are uploaded with common and predefined data fields. Description of each field is available to users in the metadata import interface, with clear definitions and examples. If a user tries to upload a faulty metadata file, the ETN system will return an error message and the file import will be halted. The error message is highly informative, providing a description of the mistake and the specific row number where the mistake is present in the upload file.

In addition, to improve the dataflow within the ETN data platform, we aim to develop common meta(data) standards across all manufacturers. We will therefore discuss with various manufacturers (e.g. Cefas Technology, Star-Oddi and Lotek) the way forward to standardise dataset formats such as headers and device mission setting metadata.

3.3.5 Test casing and cost-effective biomonitoring

We will upload dormant acoustic and archival data from WP3 partners to ETN (an overview of missing/important datasets is already available) to test the dataflow, such as the implementation and update of relevant metadata fields and quality checks. The test casing will be driven by users, enabling a relevant and user-friendly improvement of the data system, promoting its application in Europe and beyond. Additionally, as data on archival tagging are scarce, we will tag 50 eels in Belgium to test case the dataflow to EMODnet Biology.

Aside from software development, we will also explore the possibilities to deploy acoustic receivers to existing infrastructure such as platforms of opportunity (POO). If successful, we will also measure environmental variables to link the species' presence to the environmental features. In addition, combining biologging and fish tracking sensors with other networks like passive acoustics is highly desirable to, e.g. understand species interactions. Further, the use of Open Protocol (OP) will be stimulated in the acoustic telemetry community. This will increase compatibility among sensors from various manufacturers and incorporate innovative protocols and cost-effective approaches into existing and arising new networks.

3.3.6 Gaps, unknowns, developments beyond DTO-BioFlow

As Movebank is planning a line of funding to facilitate data publication to GBIF (including improvements to Darwin Core standardisation), these are developments that align well with DTO-BioFlow's objectives and will be followed up closely.

3.4 Passive Acoustics

Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM) of sounds made by marine animals is an important method for estimating the distribution, density, and abundance of species that vocalise. It is particularly useful for animals that frequently produce

species-specific vocalisations. Harbour porpoises (*Phocoena phocoena*) are excellent candidates as seldom does a minute go by without a porpoise producing species-specific echolocation clicks. Thus, the cetacean passive acoustic observation network data flow will focus on these animals for data collection and analysis activities developed within DTO-BioFlow.

Raw acoustic data are time series of pressure or vector quantity of particle displacement. There are well-established standards for calibrating digital recordings of acoustic data. Modern electronics simplify the task of persistent recordings, but long-term acoustic records involve large data volumes. The biological interpretation of acoustic data requires detecting signals produced by the animals, and the development and evaluation of detectors for classification is an active area of research. Several commercial devices (C-PODs and F-PODs) which record detections of porpoise clicks are widely used; their use of standard detectors simplifies this element of the problem. Here we propose that the primary passive acoustic data to flow from ETN into EMODnet Biology; for DTO-BioFlow, these are data on the time and location of porpoise clicks.

3.4.1 Existing data flows

For the C-PODs and F-PODs sensors, manufactured by Chelonia, UK, the raw data are downloaded from the acoustic recorders deployed at sea and processed using the software developed by the manufacturer themselves. As a result of this processing, Porpoise Positive Minutes (PPMs, i.e. a minute in which at least one detection of a porpoise was detected, see below) can be determined, and the data can be exported and uploaded to ETN. In ETN, metadata linked to the project, the deployment, and the sensor is necessary before the PPM data can be uploaded. Information about the project is stored in the IMIS. Currently, a data export aggregated with an hourly resolution from the PPMs is done on a yearly basis to EMODnet Biology. The proposed data flow for the passive acoustics data is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Schematic diagram showing the passive acoustics data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow.

3.4.2 Data not in EMODnet Biology

Porpoise Positive Minutes (PPM): provides information on the presence and absence per minute of harbour porpoise in the vicinity of an active sensor for passive acoustic monitoring. Porpoise Positive Hours or Porpoise Positive Days can also be reported and are determined by aggregation to the respective time resolution. Each porpoise detection has a quality label attached to it, determined by the system's classifier, which represents how confident the algorithm is on the porpoise detection. Currently, one dataset from passive acoustic monitoring can be found on EMODnet Biology for *Phocoena phocoena* from observation network in the Belgian Part of the North Sea. Data from the Helcom Monitoring programme on Harbour Porpoise is integrated into the HELCOM Biodiversity database, the data flow of these data towards EMODNET BIOLOGY will be investigated.

In addition, several PAM monitoring projects are collecting these data in the European seas which are currently not flowing to any data repository or aggregator. For the UK and North Sea waters a comprehensive inventory has been created, commissioned by the UK Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs.

Metadata: metadata about the type of sensor and the settings used, and metadata about the deployment of the sensor are necessary but currently not included in the data available via EMODnet Biology. These metadata information should include the period of good quality recording, latitude, and longitude.

Most PAM data do not flow to EMODnet Biology or any other international data portal, except for the Baltic data that flows to the HELCOM repository.

3.4.3 Sustainable ingestion procedures into EMODnet Biology and the EU DTO

The goal for the passive acoustic data type will be to include the harbour porpoise detection data collected by C-POD and F-POD sensors into [ETN](#), as it can accommodate metadata per deployment of the acoustic sensor and exports of sensors in minute resolution. The uploaded data are assigned to a specific project and only open data (not under moratorium) are provided to EMODnet Biology, on a yearly basis following quality control procedures. The goal will be to automate this process as much as possible, thus decreasing the amount of manual work. Data intake to EMODnet Biology will be re-examined to ensure it adheres to community-supported standards. Improving the automated quality control, strict rules on metadata requirements and an automated data aggregation and export to a format compatible to the one used in EMODnet Biology are necessary steps in this process.

For the data that are not yet available in EMODnet Biology, a meta-analysis of all the PAM users will be performed to contact the right institutes and involve them first in the data standardisation and data provenance and consequently, to get them engaged in the data ingestion process.

3.4.4 Extraction and processing into harmonised and fit-for-purpose science-based data products

The SAMBAH (<http://sambah.org>) project used C-POD data to estimate the density and abundance of harbour porpoise in the Baltic Sea and to model their habitat preferences. Similar methods can be applied to the data collected in DTO-BioFlow, to provide maps of the density and abundance of harbour porpoise in the North Sea (L5 product, see Table 4). The DTO-BioFlow project will aim to develop scripts to generate these maps as new data are input into the system, and to provide more detailed maps of areas of special interest to stakeholders. As part of QC, the project will compare density and distribution estimated from visual sighting data in the North Sea (see 3.5) to that from acoustic detections and will compare detection rates of porpoise clicks from the various instruments used for this passive acoustic monitoring. Furthermore, spatial and temporal modelling methods will be applied to investigate the patterns in porpoise density alongside biological and physical oceanographic variables.

3.4.4.1 Implementation of standards, quality assurance, data models and communication protocols

In DTO-BioFlow we will identify, compare and compile standards already used for observation, data exchange and reporting for specific species/species groups and specific habitats/regions. Existing data ingestion into HELCOM database can be used as a starting point for this task. We will also look at the standardisation in sensor deployment, calibration and the incorporation of sounds associated with specific behaviours into the data flow.

3.4.5 Test casing and cost-effective biomonitoring

The deployment of multiple autonomous sensors will be tested to improve cost-effective monitoring as well as methods to co-analyse data from multiple sensors to bridge the knowledge gaps in ecosystem dynamics. The focus will be on the integration of acoustic telemetry data and PAM sensors to evaluate the co-occurrence of top predators (e.g. fish and marine mammals) in the marine ecosystem. Deploying multiple passive acoustic sensors and testing their compatibility is important for intercomparison of long-term data series as well as providing complementary insight in the occurrence

and behaviour of those species. In the light of DTO-BioFlow, the useability of Ships Of Opportunity (SOO) as well as the sustainability of citizen science PAM measurements will be evaluated.

The existing PAM programmes in different regions will be reviewed in terms of target species, data flow and their readiness to be included in the data stream for the EU DTO Data Lake.

3.4.6 Gaps, unknowns, developments beyond DTO-BioFlow

One data gap involves finding historic datasets for entry into DTO-BioFlow as, even though we focus on ongoing data collection, historic data have their own particular value. Detection and classification of marine animal sounds is a highly active field of bioacoustics. As digital infrastructures such as the EU DTO Data Lake develop capacities for large datasets, it will become more feasible to store raw acoustic data in an analysis system that enables testing of different detectors and classifiers to improve the quality of the estimates of which species are present. Analysis of density and abundance requires estimates of the rates at which animals call, which can be quantified with biologging data from acoustic recording tags, or acoustic locations if the individual animal can be tracked. Consequently, a longer-term goal, beyond the project's lifetime, would be the development of an underwater sound library of species' vocalisations, which will be a powerful tool in improving the detection and classification of vocalising species in marine waters, with a focus on species that vocalise less than porpoises.

3.5 Other Networks

This section addresses data types and sources not covered previously in this document, it includes species occurrence data from global platforms not yet included in EMODnet Biology, gridded species distributions from various projects, reporting data addressing EU Directives, industry, citizen science, and literature data. The data sources in this section are vary widely, and a lot of the specific details to bring these data into the EU DTO still require further discussion and planning with the other WPs to, for example, identify other relevant biodiversity data sources that can be useful to the DUCs in WP4.

3.5.1 Existing data flows

As mentioned above, the data types and sources covered in this section are diverse and are, by definition, not covered by any of the established data flows for common data types. We therefore refer to the general data flow in Figure 1 but with the reservation that variations may be identified for specific data subtypes in the future.

This section also covers data that have been published to data integrators such as OBIS and GBIF but are not yet ingested into EMODnet Biology. This is because some marine publishers are more strongly associated with the GBIF network and do not feel the need to publish to OBIS, no connection has been made with the OBIS network yet, or because they are not based in Europe and therefore publish through an OBIS node other than EurOBIS. If there is some compatibility at least at the data format level, there is an option to ingest the data from the publisher IPT into EMODnet Biology, although this is *ad hoc* and there is no automated ingestion from GBIF publishers in place at the moment.

SCANS: Cetacean sighting data from SCANS I and II are available in EMODnet Biology through a connection with the OBIS SEAMAP node.

European Seabirds at Sea (ESAS): occurrence data are already in EMODnet Biology and an established workflow has been implemented via ICES.

Industry data: existing data flows are from EMODnet Ingestion towards EMODnet Biology, but they are insufficient for the demonstrator's purposes in terms of datasets and regional coverage.

3.5.2 Data not in EMODnet Biology

Literature-based data: data are directly sourced from different data integrators (Plazi, OpenBioDiv, and SIBiLS, also including other actors) and submitted to the relevant repositories/aggregators according to their type and are not currently in EMODnet Biology. This type of data requires significant human resources to be made available in a format

which is compatible with the one used in EMODnet Biology. This is a line of work that cannot be achieved during the project's lifetime and therefore the work will be limited to identifying suitable datasets in each integrator.

Research grade iNaturalist observations available in GBIF: for data collected via the OBIS UK node, a current workflow is in place for additional validation and quality assurance. A periodic download of 'research grade' observations are passed to the iRecord platform (<https://irecord.org.uk/>), its community includes several volunteer experts who manually review and validate the observations (<https://irecord.org.uk/help/records-verified>). Whilst this approach addresses concerns over 'research grade' observations coming from the iNaturalist platform, the solution is not scalable for a greater number of taxa or over a larger geographical coverage. EMODnet Biology will republish data that are verified by an expert taxonomist, those that will mostly be UK data, for other iNaturalist data where it is not possible to assess if they were reviewed by an expert, a direct data flow to the EU DTO should be implemented instead.

eBird: data are available in GBIF but not in EMODnet Biology. By reusing the existing connection between GBIF and EMODnet Biology, data verified by experts will be republished and any data that does not fit this criterion should flow directly to the EU DTO instead.

Species and habitat range maps: will be available soon from AquaMaps, AquaX, and the MPA Europe project. AquaMaps provides expert reviewed as well as unreviewed species range maps and future range maps through its portal under a CC-BY-NC license. The MPA Europe project will publish species and habitat range maps for Europe through the OBIS data products portal.

SCANS: Cetacean sighting data from SCANS III and IV have not entered the system as they are also not available in other data repositories or integrators. This is a line of work that will be pursued the relevant organisations during the project's lifetime.

European Seabirds at Sea (ESAS): The derived data products such as density maps are not available in EMODnet Biology and will be mobilised during the project's lifetime.

Traits data: are required to support the development of use cases in WP4. The central repository for traits is WoRMS, but the focus has been to ensure good coverage of a limited number of traits. Other platforms (e.g. BIOTIC, Polytraits, Fishbase, PLET, etc.) exist and have historically contributed to WoRMS.

Through DUC 4.5 focussing on ecosystem-based spatial planning and MPA management, an operational, API-based publication endpoint of traits data from BIOTIC will be established.

Industry data: it is too early at this point to mention the different data sources that will be harvested. We know that in many countries there are marine monitoring activities related to industrial activity (e.g. windfarm developments). The idea is to stimulate external sources to submit their biodiversity data to EMODnet Biology, encouraging the use of the existing EMODnet Ingestion data submission system. Data submission via this service will be promoted in the network of DTO-BioFlow partners and their extended network, complementing the activities done in EMODnet Ingestion and their network. The partners will be targeted by email and follow-up meetings will be setup as/when applicable where data requests will be sent to identified parties/contact persons from the network. Complementing the activities already in place by EMODnet Ingestion is a first step towards encouraging data publication, however other lines of work might be pursued if it is found that the outcome is insufficient.

Other candidates such as the Ocean Data Platform (<https://www.huboccean.earth/platform>) and [Ocean Decade Data Group](#) will also be explored. A limited number of unstructured datasets from the UK's Crown Estate's Marine Data Exchange platform (<https://www.marinedataexchange.co.uk/>) that have been collected by the renewables sector are being progressed to EMODnet Biology via the UK OBIS node. It is expected that these data will serve as a pilot to a more operational dataflow being developed in the next few years.

Lastly, the semi-automated identification of European marine datasets in GBIF will be pursued and implemented during the project's lifetime.

3.5.3 Sustainable ingestion procedures into EMODnet Biology and the EU DTO

Considering the data flows already established, it is not envisioned that new developments are required as the data flows are of a frequent nature.

3.5.4 Extraction and processing into harmonised and fit-for-purpose science-based data products

This task will not create new products based on available data but instead identify those that can be (re)published via EMODnet Biology and/or the EU DTO. Additionally, range maps and density maps will be provided by several platforms and projects, including those listed in Table 2.

3.5.4.1 Implementation of standards, quality assurance, data models and communication protocols

Literature-based data are closely connected to the area of standards and data models. For example, one of the data sources (OpenBiodiv) involves an ontology about biodiversity ([OpenBiodiv-O](#)). Similarly, SIBiLS makes use of [different vocabularies](#) to process its results, while TreatmentBank (from Plazi) has a strong emphasis on implementing the FAIR principles.

For industry data the main objective will be to encourage data providers in submitting all relevant information, if possible by adhering to the biodiversity standards.

Lastly, an assessment of new automated quality checks for citizen science data will be done and implemented if feasible.

3.5.5 Test casing and cost-effective biomonitoring

As this task is not focused on a specific type of data or data source, there is no information to be added to this section at the time of writing this document.

3.5.6 Gaps, unknowns, developments beyond DTO-BioFlow

Several lines of work can be identified beyond the project's lifetime, these include, for example:

- For literature data an internal inventory of datasets that should be digitised and made available through EMODnet Biology;
- For citizen science data, an assessment of the possibilities for scaling up the data flow implemented for UK data in iNaturalist to cover the European Seas;
- Industry data is notoriously difficult to publish due to commercial sensitivities. It is possible that not all activities planned during DTO-BioFlow will be finalised due the constraints this sector has.

4. Conclusions

- The data flow towards the EDITO data lake can largely be organized through EMODnet Biology. For some products a direct connection between integrator/repository systems and the EDITO data lake may be needed.
- Although in different stages of development, for most of the considered data types there are already integrators/repositories and some initial data flows existing. For each of them, current gaps and needs were identified and tangible steps forward were described in this Blueprint.
- The current document aimed to cover the existing data flows and the future improvements that we envision for each of the data types. Nonetheless, the data flows proposed should remain open and flexible enough to accommodate any changes necessary, as the different technologies and standards for each data type advance.

